

Questionnaire

1 General Information

- Do you agree to participate in the survey and for us to use the data you provide for research anonymously?
- 1. What is your age?
- 2. What is your role?
- 3. What is your organisation's domain?
- 4. How familiar are you with Large Language Models (LLM)? *Large Language Models are deep learning models that power chatbots (ex., ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot) and perform natural language tasks (ex., text generation and translation). LLMs in software engineering can be used to learn new concepts, get guidance to solve a problem, and generate software artefacts, such as code or architecture. Mark only one oval.*
 - Not at all familiar: You have no knowledge of LLMs.
 - Slightly familiar: You have heard of LLMs but have very little understanding of what they are or how they work.
 - Familiar: You have a general idea of the purpose and applications of LLMs.
 - Very familiar: You have a good understanding of LLMs. You are knowledgeable about their capabilities, and limitations. You can assess what LLM can help with which task.

2 About the use of LLMs

1. How often do you use LLMs at work? Mark only one oval.
 - I do not use it at all at work
 - Occasionally (only when I'm stuck on a task/problem)
 - On a weekly basis
 - On a daily basis
 - Other:

2. Briefly describe what LLMs you use and for what purpose in your work.
3. Write three expectations from LLMs that are most important for you when using them at work
4. Explain how you feel when you receive an incorrect answer from an LLM?
5. What do you typically do after receiving an incorrect answer from an LLM? Mark only one oval.
 - Provide feedback
 - Change the prompt
 - Switch to another LLM.
 - I do not do anything
 - Other:
6. Describe how your motivation to continue your task is affected if your interaction with the LLM did not assist you as intended with that task.
7. Describe a situation where you felt frustrated when using LLMs. What did you expect and what was the actual response?
8. What improvements would you like to see in LLMs to make the experience less frustrating?
9. Rate how important each of these factors is in leading to a frustrating experience¹.

	Extremely Important	Very important	Im-	Moderately Important	Slightly Im-	portant	Not Important
Hallucination*							
Intention not understood							
Performance issues (e.g., LLM's server is down)							
Incorrect responses							
LLM refuses to answer							

¹*Hallucination is a phenomenon where the model generates incorrect, nonsensical, or unreal text.